

NBSINFRA

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City lab Booklet

Fingal

Ireland

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Acknowledgments

All the City Labs

The **NBSINFRA** project has **five city labs across Europe** that are assessing **how cities can handle different challenges and stay resilient through Nature-Based Solutions**. Each city lab aims to investigate how NBS can protect local infrastructure, preserve biodiversity, restore ecosystems and confront the challenges of climate change. The goal is to deliver tailored solutions and risk indicators for specific locations, contribute to city contingency plans and **increase the resilience and sustainability of NBS for future generations**.

Nature Based Solutions stages across City Labs

1	(Co-) Diagnosis and (Co-) Characterization Collaborative assessment of the current conditions and identification of key challenges and opportunities.
2	(Co-) Design and (Co-) Creation Co-designing and co-creating nature-based solutions with input from diverse stakeholders.
3	(Co-) Implementation Collaborative implementation of the solutions, ensuring active participation from all involved parties.
4	(Co-) Evaluation and (Co-) Monitoring Ongoing evaluation and monitoring of the solutions effectiveness through collective input and feedback.
5	(Co-) Amplification or (Co-) Replication Expanding or replicating the solutions collaboratively to ensure broader impact and scalability.

Ruse
Bulgaria

NBS stages: 1

Fingal
Ireland

NBS stages: 1-2

Aveiro
Portugal

NBS stages: 1-2

Prague
Czechia

NBS stages: 3-4

Cologne
Germany

NBS stages: 4

Visit our website for a more accurate insight on the project's city labs

www.nbsinfra.eu

Fingal

Ireland

Introduction

Swords, the county town of Fingal and a thriving suburban town faces various challenges related to extreme weather, ageing infrastructure and significant population growth.

As part of the NBSINFRA project, Swords has been selected as a study area where nature-based solutions (NBS) will be integrated into the Local Area Plan, focusing on protecting critical infrastructure from extreme weather and flooding. The project aims to enhance green infrastructure and climate resilience. A distinctive opportunity exists to integrate NBS into the town's future

development plans. The council plans to establish a green necklace of open spaces encircling the town, including new parks and woodlands to prevent urban sprawl, promote compact growth and create natural buffers against extreme weather events, all while fostering biodiversity and improving the town's sustainability.

Diagnosis and characterization

The categorization and diagnosis of the case study involved several essential analyses. These included identifying and characterizing the spatial distribution of hazards and social vulnerability, integrating this information with critical infrastructure (CI) and incorporating fieldwork to gather community perspectives to determine critical and vulnerable areas impacted by hazards. Flood risk mapping in Fingal highlights the significant areas vulnerable to both coastal and fluvial flooding. The case study focuses on Swords, the county town of Fingal which is prone to fluvial flooding.

Coastal and Fluvial (River) Flooding

Coastal flooding occurs when water from the sea (along the coast or in estuaries) overflows onto adjacent land or overtops coastal flood defences where these exist. Fluvial flooding occurs when rivers and other watercourses burst their banks and water flows out onto the adjacent low-lying areas (the natural floodplains).

Consequences of flooding

The consequences of flooding are determined by the impacts associated with the flooding and the vulnerability of people, property and environmental assets potentially affected by a flood.

Flood zones

Flood Zones are geographical areas within which the likelihood of flooding is in a particular range. Swords is primarily affected by fluvial flooding. In Fluvial Flood Zone A, the probability of flooding from rivers is highest, exceeding 1% (1 in 100). In Fluvial Flood Zone B, the probability of river flooding is moderate, ranging between 0.1% (1 in 1000) and 1% (1 in 100).

Critical Infrastructure

Critical Infrastructure is defined as an asset, system or part thereof which is essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions, health, safety, security and economic or social well-being of the people and the disruption or destruction of which would have a significant impact in the landscape as a result of failure to maintain those functions.

Network analysis

Swords has good road links due to its proximity to Dublin, the main focus of the Irish road network. A network analysis identifies critical links and edges essential for connecting people to critical infrastructure and assesses the impact of flood hazards on these connections. In network analysis, a node represents a point, such as an intersection, while an edge is a connection, like a road between two nodes.

In Swords, the network consists of around 1,300 nodes and 2,800 edges. Specifically, in Fluvial Flood Zone A, there are 7 nodes and 20 edges, whereas in Fluvial Flood Zone B, there are 17 nodes and 40 edges within the flood zones. This highlights the potential impact of flood hazards on connectivity.

Community engagement

In 2023 Fingal County Council adopted the Fingal Development Plan, which is an umbrella planning document defining specific strategies and policies aimed to shape the county's built environment. To support the translation of the objectives of the Development Plan at a local level in Swords, Fingal County Council and UCD jointly promoted a community engagement program as part of the planning process. This program aimed to inform the draft of the Local Area Plan for the County's administrative centre, the town of Swords from a bottom-up level.

Broad community engagement

To map the needs and ideas of residents of Swords, community engagement activities were organised in two phases. In the first phase, a crowd-mapping approach was taken to obtain a broader insight from the community. In September 2024, a digital tool called Cartospot was launched both online and at drop-in centres in Swords. Cartospot is a mapping tool that collects observations, comments and multimedia data using georeferencing to add points to a map. Through this, citizens had an opportunity to use the Cartospot mapping tool and identify specific areas which according to them were valuable as well as those at risk.

After more than 50 various Cartospot entries, the results were systematised into 3 categories: Environment, Urban Mobility and Urban Planning. The results were used as input data for the next phase of community engagement.

Focused co-creation

The next phase of the process focused on a two-day workshop with the local community to reflect on the entries gathered using Cartospot mapping and use them as prompts to co-create specific planning solutions for Swords.

On Day 1 of the workshop, participants were divided into three groups, each representing one of the three categories identified from Phase 1. Each group consisted of 3-5 participants and was guided by a facilitator and a subject expert. The role of the facilitator was to manage the discussion, whereas the expert was brought in to support the group's focus discussion through knowledge exchange. Throughout the process, the groups developed specific ideas and proposals for the town and generated analogue maps in the process. The maps created on Day 1 were used as the foundation for the Day 2 of the workshop.

Day 2 was facilitated using Geodesignhub developed by Dr Hrishikesh Ballal. It is a specialised software designed for negotiation-based planning. Participants were reorganised into two mixed groups, each tasked with developing a specific strategy for Swords based on the ideas generated earlier on Day 1. Geodesignhub helped the groups to select design or planning solutions which were now represented as polygons on the GeodesignHub and integrate them into their strategies for Swords. Later groups also compared their strategies with each other which provided a better understanding of the areas where they aligned and differed.

Representatives from Fingal County Council joined Day 2 to review and reflect on the groups' outcomes, which facilitated the final stage of the negotiation process. The session concluded with a negotiated and agreed strategy for the town by the participants, which concluded the final stage of the community engagement process.

Prospects

The outcomes of the workshop will play a crucial role in informing the draft of the Local Area Plan for Swords. By integrating the community-driven ideas generated during the community engagement activities and supported by different field experts, the integrated plan can reflect an inclusive and locally tailored vision for the town's future sustainable urban development.

For more information on the community engagement process, access the NBSinfra [Story Map](#) for Swords.

Key activities

Completed activities

- Collection of input data
- Categorization of coastal and fluvial (river) flooding
- Identification of consequences of flooding
- Broad community engagement activities
- Focused co-creation workshops
- Critical infrastructure analysis
- Network analysis
- Mapping of stakeholder groups

Future activities

- Development of a resilience-based framework
- Systematize the workshop input towards a report to inform a local area plan
- Interviews/focus groups with the County Council
- Integrating geo-design and citizens' assemblies

Best practices

Fingal City Lab has identified some valuable lessons while conducting recent activities such as flood hazard identification, resilience-based analysis and community engagement. By listing these lessons as best practices below we hope they provide insights and inform other projects and help decision-makers, city councils, decision-makers and practitioners who may work with similar conditions.

- Use ArcGIS StoryMaps and tools like CartoSpot to enhance community participation in mapping. Conduct in-person workshops to engage stakeholders and incorporate diverse perspectives.
- Leverage expert insights to support community engagement and introduce negotiation methods to align varied perspectives in planning and decision-making.
- Mapping the evolution of the proposed planning solutions from the early to final stages of the participatory process.
- Identify flood-prone areas, conduct scenario-based simulations to evaluate risks to transportation, utilities, and essential services, and apply network analysis to pinpoint critical infrastructure.

NBSINFRA

“Nature-based Solutions address societal challenges through actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems, benefiting people and nature at the same time.

They target major challenges like climate change, disaster risk reduction, food and water security, biodiversity loss and human health, and are critical to sustainable development.”

International Union for Conservation of Nature

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